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NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF THE FIRST BOOSTER STAGE TONE NOISE AT DIFFERENT OPERATIONAL CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

The results of the numerical and experimental investigation of the tone noise of the first booster stage of the high bypass ratio fan for two operational conditions $N=53.9\%$ and $N=75.5\%$ are presented. The investigation was performed using the frequency domain numerical method of multistage turbomachines tone noise simulation, developed in CIAM (Central Institute of Aviation Motors) and implemented in the 3DAS (3 Dimensional Acoustics Solver) in-house solver. The results of the computation were compared with the experimental data obtained in the CIAM C-3A acoustic test facility. The aim was to perform validation of the computational method and to investigate the mechanisms of tone noise generation in multistage turbomachine. In general satisfactory correspondence between calculation and experiment was obtained. It was shown, that the sound power of acoustic radiation through an inlet at operational conditions $N=75.5\%$ was higher than at operational conditions $N=53.9\%$, however it was distributed through larger number of tones, and as a result, the power of radiation for the strongest tones were lower than those at $N=53.9\%$ conditions.

NOMENCLATURE

N	corrected fan speed, %
Ω	shaft angular frequency (rad/s)
f, ω	frequency, angular frequency
m	circumferential order
t, x, r, θ	time and cylindrical coordinate
$C-Z$	upper indexes denoting groups of rows and their reference frames: 1 – for group of stator rows, 2 for group of rotor rows

A and B	superscripts refer correspondingly to group of rows being stationary or rotating in the current reference frame
N^C	number of stators rows in a C-th group of rows
μ	$= 1..N^C$ - number of a row in C-th group
B_μ^C	number of blades in μ -th row in C-th group
gcd	greatest common divisor
P^C	$= gcd(B_1^C, \dots, B_N^C)$
j_μ^C	arbitrary integer constants
J^B	number of harmonic of shaft angular frequency in reference frame connected with A-th group
J^B	$= j^B/P^B$ number of harmonic of base frequency in the reference frame connected with A-th group
q	number of harmonic fragment
Q_μ^C	$= B_\mu^C/P^C$
$\Delta\Psi$	phase lag
U	vector of conservative variables
F_μ^C	vector of conservative variables for harmonic fragment (harmonic subcomponent)
n	number of blade channel in a row which corresponds to the specified value of θ (starts from zero)
θ_{bb}	angular coordinate, which describes position of a point inside the blade passage
s, s_{max}	scattering index, maximum scattering index
I, h, a, e, w	arbitrary integers

f_{μ} blade passing frequency (BPF) of the μ -th rotor in a compressor: $f_{\mu} = B_{\mu}^2 \Omega / 2\pi$

INTRODUCTION

The advances in the suppression of fan noise of aviation engines made more notable the contribution of other noise sources to the engine noise, such as booster stages and low pressure turbine [1]. Up to the present moment this component of noise is not given special attention at designing of aviation engines. However booster stages and turbine noise can become a concern for future engines as the fan noise is further reduced, especially in the geared turbofans with increased low pressure shaft rotation speeds.

In general, the noise of the booster stages of modern fans is not negligibly small. For example, in the work, presented in [2], the full-scale test results (engine static tests) were compared with the model scale fan test results (research fan rig without low pressure compressor). On the bases of such comparison it was suggested that compressor tone and broadband noise may be significant components of the inlet noise. The compressor contribution to the tone noise was especially strong at approach conditions.

The analysis of available data on narrowband spectra of turbofans shows, that well notable tones at blade passing frequencies of booster stages rotors and at frequencies been combinations of these frequencies with the blade passing frequency of a fan are often observed at approach conditions or operational conditions with lower shaft rotation speeds [3, 4].

In this paper the high bypass ratio fan model with booster stages developed in CIAM is investigated. For this fan at approach conditions ($N=53.9\%$) the tones connected with the booster stages have much higher sound pressure levels than the tones on the harmonics of blade passing frequency of the fan rotor [5]. In fig. 1 is shown narrowband spectrum of the fan model in the forward hemisphere at 60° and are marked the tones being the harmonics of the fan blade passing frequency and the tones connected with the first, the second and the third booster stages. The radiation from the booster stages definitely prevails in the forward hemisphere.

With the shaft rotation speed growth, the contribution of this tones decrease, and eventually becomes indistinguishable against the noise of multiple pure tones. Intuitively the dominance of the fan noise among other sources when the fan is working at transonic operational condition and its tone noise is mainly determined by the shock wave structure, rotating with the rotor blades, seems natural as this structure rapidly increases with the growth of the shaft speed. However the strength of the highest booster tones starts to decrease at speeds lower than those at which shock waves, connected with the rotor became capable to propagate outside through the inlet and the multiple pure tones appears. For example at operational conditions $N=75.5\%$, the noise of shock waves is cut-off, but the contribution of booster tones is barely visible in the spectrum. The strength of the fan blade passing frequency tones increase in comparison with the $N=53.9\%$ conditions while the strength of the tones, connected with the first

booster stage remain nearly the same, and the strength of the other booster stages tones radically decrease (fig. 2). One of the main motivations of this work is to find the explanation of this effect.

Fig. 1 Narrowband spectrum of the fan model in the forward hemisphere (60°) at $N=53.9\%$. Four main families of tones are highlighted a) harmonics of BPF $f=h f_1$; b) combinations $f=h f_1+f_2$; c) combinations $f=h f_1+f_3$; d) combinations $f=h f_1+f_4$ (h – natural number)

Fig. 2 Narrowband spectrum of fan model in front hemisphere (60°) at $N=75.5\%$. Two main families of tones are highlighted a) harmonics of BPF $f=h f_1$; b) combinations $f=h f_1+f_2$. Other families of tones are barely noticeable.

The feature of booster stages as noise sources in comparison with the fan is that in their case noise is determined by an interaction of several blade rows. Even if there is one booster stage, it contains three blade rows, and its noise while propagating outside the engine, should pass through or be reflected by the fan rotor.

The tone noise of the multistage turbomachine can't be described as simple set of tones, arising in the interactions of separate pairs of rows with different rotation speeds. While propagating through a turbomachine, spiral wave, generated by some rotor-stator interaction, undergoes scattering or by stators, with the change of its circumferential mode order, or by rotors with the change of both the circumferential mode order and the frequency. Thus many tones with frequencies, being combinations of blade passing frequencies of different

rotors are generated, as clearly seen in fig. 1. The energy distribution between tones depends both on the geometry of a turbomachine, and from the turbomachine operational conditions.

In CIAM for calculation of multistage turbomachines tone noise the linear frequency domain method was developed. The method is based on the kinematic relations featuring dependence of flow fields in a turbomachine from time and circumferential angle. It allows quite simple actuation of complex interactions between rows into the computation. The method was implemented in the 3DAS CIAM in-house solver [6,7]. Earlier this method was used for the calculation of the tone noise of the first booster stage of the fan model under consideration at approach operational conditions [8]. The results of the calculation showed satisfactory correspondence with experimental data.

The current paper is devoted to the calculation of the first booster stage tone noise at the N=75.5% operational conditions. The results of the enhanced calculation for the N=53.9% operational conditions will also be presented. The paper includes the investigation of the mechanisms of the tone noise generation in the booster stage and also the comparison between the results of the calculations with each other and with the experimental data for the additional validation of the computational method.

The structure of the paper is the following. In the first section we will write out the kinematic relations, featuring dependence of flow fields in a turbomachine from time and circumferential angle. The description will follow [8,9] but will be expressed in a more general form. Then the approach for frequency domain calculations setup in the multistage turbomachine will be discussed. After that the short description of the 3DAS solver will be presented. The object of investigation will be introduced in the subsequent part. In the final section the setup of the calculation, its results and their analysis will be presented.

KINEMATIC RELATIONS FOR UNSTEADY FLOW FIELD IN A MULTISTAGE TURBOMACHINE

Let's assume that a multistage turbomachine contains two groups of rows – stationary stators rows and rotating rotors rows. The flow field can be treated either in the reference frame connected with the one group of rows or in the reference frame connected with the other. The superscript A will be used to denote current reference frame and the group of rows being stationary in it, while the superscript B will denote group of rows rotating in it. The value of superscript equal to 1 will denote stators, to 2 – rotors.

Generalizing the well-known relations of Tyler and Sofrin [10] for the case of multistage turbomachine, it is not difficult to show [11] that the fields of unsteady flow parameters U in the turbomachine flow duct can be presented in the reference frame A as a superposition of the following components (circumferential modes):

$$U_{j^A j^B}(x, r, \theta^A, t) = U_{j^A j^B}(x, r) e^{i(m\theta^A - \omega^A t)} \quad (1)$$

$$m = j^A + j^B, \quad \omega^A = j^B \Omega^{AB}$$

where Ω^{AB} – is the angular frequency of rotation of the group of rows B relative to the group of rows A, and

$$j^A = \sum_{\mu=1}^{N^A} j_{\mu}^A B_{\mu}^A, \quad j^B = \sum_{\mu=1}^{N^B} j_{\mu}^B B_{\mu}^B \quad (2)$$

When the group of rows A corresponds to the group of stators, than $\Omega^{AB} = \Omega$, otherwise $\Omega^{AB} = -\Omega$. The values of azimuth angles in the reference frames connected with the groups of rows A and B are connected by the relationship $\theta^B = \theta^A - \Omega^{AB} t$.

The possible values of numbers j^C (C-Z superscripts denote just some group of rows), which uniquely characterize the circumferential mode, are not arbitrary. The necessary and sufficient condition for the existence of solutions (there may be infinitely many) of Diophantine equation of the kind

$$w = I_1 a_1 + \dots + I_e a_e$$

where I_1, \dots, I_e – a specified set of integer numbers, is the proportionality of w to a greatest common divisor of numbers I_k – $gcd(I_1, \dots, I_e)$. So each if those numbers corresponds to the infinite number of sets of integers $\{j^C_{\mu}\}$, and are proportional to some arbitrary integers, j^C with proportionality coefficients P^C , characterizing the number of spatial periods of group of rows in the full annulus. Therefore the frequencies $P^2 \Omega^{j^2}$ and $P^1 \Omega^{j^1}$ are the basic frequencies of tone noise in the stator and in the rotor reference frames. The expression for the unsteady flow field U in the reference frame A can be written as:

$$U^A = \sum_{j^B=-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i(\theta^A P^B - P^B \Omega^{AB} t) j^B} \sum_{j^A=-\infty}^{\infty} U_{j^A j^B}(x, r) e^{i\theta^A P^A j^A} \quad (3)$$

These expressions are equivalent to the corresponding expressions for the single stage with P^2 blades in the rotor and P^1 blades in the stator.

According to the (3) the flow field in a turbomachine can be represented as a series of flow fields of harmonics of basic frequencies. In the blocks connected with the μ -th row in the group of rows A it is possible to write out:

$$U_{\mu}^A(t, x, r, \theta^A) = \sum_{j^B=-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-iP^B \Omega^{AB} j^B t} U_{\mu j^B}^A(x, r, \theta^A) \quad (4)$$

Moreover if the value of P^A is not equal 1, it is enough to perform calculation in the sector equal to the $1/P^A$ part of the full annulus. The flow field outside this sector can be determined using phase-lagged boundary conditions.

Let's consider the sector with the size $2\pi/P^A$ radian in the μ -th row of the group of rows A. It is possible to divide this sector into $Q_{\mu}^A = B_{\mu}^A/P^A$ equal blade passages. In each of this passages the angular coordinate θ_{bb} , which describes the position of the point in the blade passage relative to its borders, can be introduced. This angular coordinate may be defined in such a way, that in the n -th blade passage $\theta^A = \theta_{bb} + 2\pi/P^A \cdot n$ (n variable starts to be counted from zero).

The phase lag between the boundaries of the blade passage for the disturbance, described by (1,2), in the μ -th row of the group of rows A is:

$$\Delta\Psi_{\mu}^A = \frac{2\pi}{B_{\mu}^A} \cdot (P^B j^B + P^A j^A)$$

This phase lag is not individual for each disturbance (1,2) but is common at least for all disturbances which have common frequency and their \tilde{f}^A differs only on the value, proportional to Q_μ^A , as phase lags, which differs from each other on $2\pi a$, $a = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$, are equivalent. For any harmonic there is Q_μ^A groups of disturbances, which differ from each other by phase lag. Following the work [11], these groups of disturbances will be referred below as harmonic fragments or harmonic subcomponents. The harmonic fragment can be characterized by the number of harmonic \tilde{f}^B and the number of fragment q , ($0 \leq q \leq Q_\mu^A - 1$), such that for any disturbance in it $\tilde{f}^A = q + a \cdot Q_\mu^A$.

The interaction of a circumferential mode with the blade row B_μ^A in the reference frame, connected with the group of rows A, leads to the increment of circumferential order m in (1,2) by $\delta m = s_\mu^A B_\mu^A$, where $s_\mu^A = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$ – arbitrary scattering index. Thus the notion of harmonic fragment has strict physical meaning. It is the minimal assembly of circumferential modes, such that the interactions between those modes and the blade row B_μ^A leads to the formation of disturbances belonging to the same assembly.

The flow field in the μ -th row of the group of rows A can be expressed through the fields of harmonic fragments in the 0-th blade passage. For the specified harmonic \tilde{f}^B :

$$U_{\mu \tilde{f}^B}^A(x, r, \theta^A) = e^{i \left(\frac{2\pi n}{B_\mu^A \Omega^{AB}} \right) \tilde{f}^B p^B \Omega^{AB} Q_\mu^A - 1} \sum_{q=0}^{Q_\mu^A - 1} F_{\mu \tilde{f}^B q}^A(x, r, \theta_{bb}) e^{in \Delta \Psi_{\mu q}^A} \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta \Psi_{\mu q}^A = 2\pi / Q_\mu^A \cdot q$.

The expression (5) specifies the reconstruction of the unsteady flow field in a row from data on fields of harmonic fragments. Thus the problem of calculation of unsteady flow field in the multistage turbomachine can be formulated as the problem of calculation of some sets of fields of harmonic fragments in each stage of turbomachine. This calculation can be performed both in the linear [8] and nonlinear approximations [9]

The presented results can be simply generalized to the case of counter rotating groups of rows. Also they can be written for several groups of rows, rotating with different angular velocities.

THE FREQUENCY DOMAIN METHOD FORMULATION FOR A MULTISTAGE TURBOMACHINE

In many cases, a relatively small set of tones, commonly corresponding to harmonics of blade passing frequencies of rotors and their sums and differences, dominates in the tone noise of multistage turbomachines [1,2,3,4]. Thus frequency domain methods seem attractive approach for calculation of turbomachinery tone noise.

Frequency-domains methods are based on the assumption that the flow field in a row can be characterized by a finite (and quite small) number of harmonics [12,13]. The introduction of harmonic fragments makes possible to further reduce the computational cost, by assumption that the solution in the row for each harmonic can be characterized by some small number of harmonic fragments (much less than Q_μ^A)

[8,11]. These two statements are the bases of the frequency-domain method of multistage turbomachinery tone noise calculations, used in the current paper.

The choice of harmonic fragments in rows depends on the aim of numerical simulation. If the aim is to simulate the disturbances in a row, caused by the interaction with the adjacent rows, the calculation can be performed only for frequencies been harmonics of blade passing frequencies of the rows and only for 0-th harmonic fragments (which in this case are usually called harmonics). The examples of such calculations can be found in [14,15,16]. However, if the aim is to calculate the disturbances, generated by the nearest row of the same row group, several harmonic fragments with zero frequency should be resolved in a row (the more the higher precision). If the aim is to determine the amplitudes of strongest tones, generated by turbomachine, the construction of the suitable set of harmonic fragments is based on the hypothesis about the possible contributions of various interactions in the tone noise of turbomachine.

In the previous works [8,11] the authors developed the approach for construction of the set of harmonic fragments suitable for approximate calculation of the tone noise of multistage turbomachine at least at specified frequency range. For the construction of the approximation a simple approach based on the notion of generating sequence of modes is used. The generating sequence includes: a) initial circumferential mode – some circumferential non-uniformity of stationary flow of one of the rows, b) some sequence of intermediate circumferential modes – disturbances (no matter vortical, entropy or acoustical in nature) which forms in the interaction acts between circumferential modes and rows and participates in them again, c) outgoing circumferential mode – acoustical mode which forms in the inlet or outlet of turbomachine as a result. There is an infinite number of generating sequences connecting each possible pair of initial and outgoing modes, but only for a few pairs of modes there is significant transmission of power between them. Also even in those cases only a few generating sequences of modes participates noticeably in the process. And of course most of initial modes give quite small contribution to the tone noise of turbomachine. So our aim is just to find appropriate heuristics, which allows us to specify the generating sequences, giving significant contribution to the noise generation process.

As it was shown in [8], the heuristics can be constructed on the basis of quite simple observations on scattering characteristics of blade rows and on disturbances of steady flow field generated by them. This heuristics can be expressed as limitations on the values of integers \tilde{f}_μ^C in the sets of constants in (2), describing initial, intermediate and outgoing modes. These integers either correspond to the scattering indexes or proportional to the circumferential orders of initial modes in the shortest generating sequences, which forms the modes under consideration [8].

The main principles of mode selection can be formulated in the following way [8]. Within the framework of the presented method it is offered to carry out

calculation only for those modes (initial, intermediate and outgoing) for which exists set of constants $\{j_{\mu}^c\}$ satisfying limitation $|j_{\mu}^c| \leq s_{max}$, where s_{max} - some small integer.

Usually in our group the condition $s_{max} = 2$ is used. In general the choice of s_{max} should be determined on the bases of analyses of initial modes and scattering characteristics of blades.

The first step of the mode selection is the determination of all cut-on outgoing modes in the specified frequency range, satisfying the limitations. All this modes should be included in the calculation. Then intermediate and initial modes, correspondent for these outgoing modes are defined. Among them only those modes, for which nonzero integers $\{j_{\mu}^c\}$ coincide with corresponding integers in at least one outgoing mode (principle of minimum number of interactions) are included in the calculation. And finally, it is supposed that cut-off initial and intermediate modes can propagate upstream on a distance no longer than one row, so to reduce the number of modes, which should be resolved in the first several upstream rows.

The authors experience shows that the set of modes, obtained according to these principles, usually gives quite good approximations for the desired solution, though sometimes needs correction in the process of calculation.

At the final stage of the calculation preparation, on the bases of the set of modes, which should be resolved in a row, the set of harmonic fragments in a row, needed for its simulation is determined.

3DAS SOLVER

The method of tone noise calculation used in the 3DAS solver is based on the solution of linear or nonlinear Euler equations for disturbances over viscous steady mean flow field in the reference frames of blade rows. The calculations can be performed either in the time domain or in the frequency domain. For the spatial approximation the fourth order DRP (Dispersion Relation Preserving) scheme, rewritten for the finite volume method [17] is used. For the time derivative approximation the fourth order Runge-Kutta scheme of HALE-RK (High-Accuracy Large-step Explicit Runge-Kutta) type [18] is implemented. More details on the numerical scheme can be found in [6,7].

The input data for the solver is a steady mean flow field in the computational domain and a body-fitted computational grid. For turbomachinery tone noise applications the steady mean flow field in rows should be calculated using Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations, finite volume spatial approximation and "mixing-plane" interfaces between rows.

The method of a multistage turbomachine tone noise calculation based on the notion of harmonic fragment is implemented in 3DAS solver and can be used both in the frameworks of a linear frequency-domain method and a nonlinear harmonic balance method. This paper devoted to the calculations in the linear approximation, which was described in [8].

In this approximation the calculations for different harmonic fragments in a row are performed

independently. Thus the approach reduces computational domain to a single blade passage for each row. The boundary conditions on the periodic boundaries of the blade passage are specified by (5). The interaction between rows is provided using special interfaces, which preserve the continuity of specified circumferential modes [8] on the inter-row boundaries.

For the analysis of a flow field in a turbomachine and for the construction of sources for a task of calculation of noise propagation through an inlet and a nozzle, a procedure for the decomposition of unsteady flow field on acoustic modes in the cylindrical coaxial channel at some surface orthogonal to the shaft is implemented in the solver. If the steady flow field has a radial nonuniformity and/or a swirl, the solution for modes is calculated numerically, using the technique described in [12]. Otherwise, the well known analytical expressions for the modes in a coaxial cylindrical channel with a uniform mean flow are used [10].

3DAS solver also implements several other computational methods which simplify performing calculation of turbomachinery tone noise in the far field. First of all should be mentioned the method based on the Ffowcs-Williams and Hawkings equation with a penetrable data (integration) surface. The description of these methods can be found in [7].

THE OBJECT OF INVESTIGATION

The fan under consideration is a 700 mm diameter high bypass ratio wide chord fan model with swept stator vanes, designed for an advanced turbofan of civil aircraft. It has three booster stages. The description of the model can be found in [5,8] and in references therein.

In the configuration under consideration the model has 18 blades in the fan rotor and 41 vanes in the stator of bypass duct. It also has 71 vanes in the inlet guide vanes (IGV) of the booster stages, 86 blades in the rotor of the first booster stage and 100 blades in the stator of the first stages. Besides two other booster stages, the model also contained 8 struts in the bypass duct and 9 supporting struts in the exit of the bypass duct. The scheme of a fan model in the test rig setup can be seen in the fig. 3

In the paper two operational conditions of the fan model are considered. The first operational condition correspond to approach condition with the relative shaft speed $N=53.9\%$. It is characterised by subsonic flow field in the blade rows. The second operational condition correspond to relative shaft speed $N=75.5\%$. There are regions of flow with supersonic relative Mach number in the fan rotor for this condition. However the tip speeds of the rotor blades are low enough to prevent the formation of multiple pure tones noise. Some design parameters of the fan model at approach, $N=75.5\%$ and designed mode are represented in Table 1.

Fig. 3. Scheme of the fan model: a) general view; b) magnified fragment

Table 1. Parameters of the fan model

	Design	N=75.5%	Approach
Fan rotor tip speed, m/s	395	298.2	212.9
First stage rotor tip speed, m/s	221.5	167.2	119.4
Bypass ratio	8.5	8.99	9.7

The aim of calculations was to resolve the main tones, generated by the first booster stage of the fan model. The experience obtained in the previous calculation showed [8] that the tones, which frequencies are the combinations of f_2 with some harmonic of f_1 , arise as a result of the scattering of the disturbance with the frequency equal to f_2 on the fan rotor. Therefore, first of all, there was a task in view to correctly describe mechanisms of generation of the tone with this frequency in the booster stage. To increase the precision of the calculation, it was also decided to take into account the mechanisms of tones generation at frequencies f_2-f_1 and f_2+f_1 . These tones are also well appreciable on in the narrowband spectra, obtained in the experiment.

The test campaign for the fan in the rig setup was performed in the C-3A test facility [5]. It is designed for acoustic, aerodynamic, and mechanical investigations of counter rotating and conventional fan models. In this facility is possible to measure fan noise at forward and rear hemisphere simultaneously. The measurement system includes 24 microphones.

THE CALCULATION OF TONE NOISE

Calculation of steady flow fields

The first stage of the simulation was the computation of mean steady flow fields using RANS equations, the semi-empirical model of turbulence, and "mixing-plane" interfaces between blade rows. It was performed with CIAM in-house aerodynamic solvers "3D-IMP_MULTI" [6]. Computational domain included one blade passage for rotor stator and each row of booster stages. The boundaries of the computational domain and boundaries between blocks for individual rows were shown by black lines on the fig. 4. The size of the computational grid was 5.6 million cells. The grid had H-type. The results of computation were compared with experimental data.

Satisfactory correspondence for the fan integral characteristics was obtained for all operation range.

Fig. 4. Scheme of the computational domain: I) Low pressure compressor; II) Booster. Here: a - the boundaries of the fine grid region in the computational domain for frequency domain calculation; b - the boundaries of buffer blocks (shown only partially); c - the surface for modal analysis upstream of the fan

Fig. 5. Relative Mach number distribution at section of constant diameter $d=0.95D$, where D is the diameter of the fan

The results of the calculations for $N=53.9\%$ and $N=75.5\%$ are presented in the fig. 5 and fig. 6. On this figures the relative Mach number distributions at sections of constant diameter $d=0.95D$ and $d=0.53D$, where D is the diameter of the fan, are presented. The first section passes through the bypass duct, while the second through the booster stages. Comparing the distributions of Mach number, it is possible to make the following conclusions. The flow field for $N=53.9\%$ operational conditions is entirely subsonic, while for $N=75.5\%$ there are significant shock waves on the fan blades. However, as it was mentioned earlier, disturbances, rotating with the rotor are cut-off at both operational conditions. Also the flow field in the booster stages remains subsonic for both operational

conditions, though at N=75.5% operational conditions the flow speed is much higher.

Fig. 6. Relative Mach number distribution at section of constant diameter $d=0.53D$

Calculation of unsteady disturbances in the near field

Computational domain for unsteady simulation included domain, containing fan rotor blade, domain containing booster IGV vane, domains containing rotor and stator blades of the first booster stage and domain, containing entrance of the bypass duct. We excluded fan stator from the calculation, because our attention was attracted to the forward hemisphere, where booster noise in the experiment was more noticeable. The process of reflection of noise from the stator has been decided to neglect. Also in our calculation we neglected interaction between the noise of the first stage and the second and third stages. It is a topic of the following research devoted to the noise of these stages.

The computational grid for unsteady simulations was derived from the grid for the steady flow field calculations. The part of the grid corresponding to the entrance of the bypass duct has been rebuilt so that to have an angular size equal to the size of the part of the grid containing fan rotor. Rotation speed for this part was set equal to the shaft rotation speed. Besides, flow in it has been averaged in circumferential direction. After that for this part of the grid we were able to perform calculations for the set of harmonic fragments being equal to that used in the grid blocks connected with the rotor.

The grid was resized in X direction in order to provide the propagation of the high-frequency disturbances generated by the first booster stage without significant error. We tried to provide resolution approximately equal to 12 points per wavelength for the disturbances, corresponding to 122 harmonic of shaft rotation frequency. The last value was derived from experimental data as the highest frequency tone of the first booster stage noise with the significant strength. As the blade passing frequencies and flow speeds are quite different for N=53.9% and N=75.5% operational conditions, eventually two different

grids were obtained as a result of refinement. The boundaries of the fine grids regions in the computational domains for frequency domain calculation are shown in the fig. 4 by green lines.

Finally, to avoid unphysical reflections from the boundaries buffer zones in which grid cells are stretched near the outer boundaries were added to the grids. In these blocks outgoing waves are absorbed by numerical viscosity. The size of the grid cells near the outer boundary were set equal to the maximum wave length (in the direction normal to the boundary) of the waves expected in the solution. The boundaries of buffer blocks (partially) were shown in the fig. 4 by the blue lines.

Total number of cells in the grids was approximately 4.2 million for N=53.9% operational condition and 10.8 million for N=75.5% operational condition.

Table 2. Circumferential modes under consideration

j^2	j^1	m	Integers $\{j_{\mu}^c\}$ (j^2, j^1, j^2, j^1)
68	100	-32	(-1,0,1,-1)
68	71	-3	(-1,-1,1,0)
68	58	10	(-1,2,1,-2)
68	42	26	(-1,-2,1,1)
68	29	39	(-1,1,1,-1)
86	100	-14	(0,0,1,-1)
86	71	15	(0,-1,1,0)
86	129	-43	(0,1,1,-2)
86	58	28	(0,2,1,-2)
86	42	44	(0,-2,1,1)
104	100	4	(1,0,1,-1)
104	142	-38	(1,-2,1,0)
104	71	33	(1,-1,1,0)
104	129	-25	(1,1,1,-2)
104	58	46	(1,2,1,-2)
104	42	62	(1,-2,1,1)

We started the calculation setup from the determination of the radiated modes for each of the frequencies of interest (f_1 , f_2-f_1 and f_2+f_1), which are cut-on and satisfy conditions, stated above. The outgoing cut-on modes, which satisfy demands on integers $\{j_{\mu}^c\}$ and correspondent numbers of harmonics of shaft rotation frequency in the reference systems of the stator and the rotor groups of rows and corresponding circumferential orders are presented in Table 2. Also, the integers $\{j_{\mu}^c\}$ are presented. The specified set of modes is common for both operational conditions. We see that most of these modes are connected with the interactions between three or four

rows. The ability to handle all these interactions in one computation is an attractive feature of our method.

The next preparation stage of the calculation is the definition for each row of the corresponding set of harmonic fragments for which the evaluation in the row will be carried out. In this process we followed a technique described in the previous sections and in more details in [8]. It has been as a result shown that, both for the first, and for the second operational conditions the solution should be performed for 67 harmonic fragments: 9 in the fan rotor, 13 in the booster IGV, 23 in the rotor of the first booster stage and 22 in the stator of the booster stage.

Earlier the results of calculation for the first booster stage at approach conditions were presented in the paper [8]. The aim of that calculation was to resolve the tones corresponding to 86 and 104 harmonics of shaft rotation frequency. The calculation was performed for 46 harmonic fragments: 7 in the fan rotor, 7 in the booster IGV, 15 in the rotor of the first booster stage and 17 in the stator of the booster stage. Thus the calculation of outgoing modes at 68 harmonic of shaft rotation frequency in addition to 86 and 104, demands the inclusion of 21 harmonic fragments in the computation.

After finishing the preparation we started the calculation. It took approximately 20000 steps for solutions to converge for both operational conditions. In the intermediate stages of computation the solutions were analyzed on the surfaces in front and behind each row. Results of modal analysis showed no significant scattering with high scattering indexes, except for the scattering of upstream going waves on the fan rotor. The latter one, evidently, demanded no changes in the specified sets of harmonic fragments.

As an example we will show on fig. 7 the amplitudes of pressure fluctuations (normalized) for the harmonic fragments containing circumferential mode with $j^2=86$, $m=15$ on the mean sections of blade channels for both operational conditions. This mode as we will see later, gives the essential contribution to the compressor radiation. We see that amplitudes of pulsations for both operational conditions are quite close to each other in front of the fan. However in the booster stage the amplitudes of pressure pulsations at $N=75.5\%$ are much higher.

Fig. 7. The fields of amplitudes of pressure fluctuations (normalized) on a mean section of blade passages for the harmonic fragments containing circumferential mode with $j^2=86$, $m=15$: a) $N=53.9\%$, b) $N=75.5\%$

As the solution converged the modal analysis of the oscillations in the inlet of the fan model has been performed. The surface, on which the modal analysis was performed, is shown in fig. 4 by red line. The results of the modal analysis in the form of sound power levels of separate circumferential modes for $N=53.9\%$ and $N=75.5\%$ operational conditions are shown in fig. 8. The modes are designated by the pair of integers (j^2, m) . Further we will repeatedly use this designation. The modes which power levels are lower than those of the strongest modes on more than 20 dB are not shown. As the modal analyses was performed in the blocks, rotating with the fan model, it was possible to extract from the solution not only the modes presented in Table 2, but also the modes with higher frequencies, arising in the interactions of the modes from the Table 2 with the fan rotor. Nevertheless among these modes only the modes with frequency equal to 122 harmonic of shaft rotation frequency are shown in fig. 8., as the grid had insufficient resolution for the modes with higher frequency.

The results of the modal analysis shows, that at operational conditions $N=53.9\%$ the strongest modes are $(86, 15)$ and $(122, 22)$. The appearance of strong disturbances at 122 harmonic of shaft rotation frequency indicates that the scattering of the modes on the fan rotor plays important role in the process of noise generation by the booster stage.

At the operational conditions $N=75.5\%$ the strongest modes are $(86, 15)$ and $(104, 33)$. We see quite different distributions of power between modes for different operational conditions. Also there is no indication of the growth of sound power with the increase of the shaft rotation speed. Contrary to the expectations, the power of modes, presented in fig. 8 for $N=75.5\%$ conditions is 2.6 dB lower than for $N=53.9\%$ operational conditions. The explanation of this unexpected behavior will be further discussed in the subsection devoted to the analysis of the computational results.

Also, it should be noted, that all modes in the fig. 8, belongs only to three harmonic fragments. The first one describes the disturbances, arising in the interaction between the rotor of the booster stage and its stator, and scattering of this interactions on the fan rotor. For it

$j^2=86+a*18$ and $m=-14+a*18$. The other two harmonic fragments correspond to disturbances arising in the interactions between the booster IGV, the rotor of the booster stage and the fan rotor. For them $j^2=86+a*18$ and $m=15+a*18$ and $m=-56+a*18$ correspondingly. The other interactions, which involve both the IGV and the stator of the booster stage, give no significant contribution to the noise of the booster stage.

Fig. 8. Results of the modal analysis upstream of the fan for operational conditions N=53.9% and N=75.5%. The modes are designated by the pair of integers (j²,m).

Additional modal decompositions were performed on the surface in front of the booster IGV and after the booster stage. The data obtained will be used in the section devoted to the analysis of the computational results.

Calculation of noise propagation to the far field

The results of modal analysis were used to set sources for noise propagation problem in the inlet. The method of calculation and geometry of computational domain completely corresponded to those described in the paper [8]. For calculation of noise propagations we used linearized Euler equations for circumferential modes in the frequency domain, specified on the longitudinal section of the inlet [7]. The computational domain is shown in the fig. 9. Its right boundary coincides with the surface for modal analysis (see fig. 4).

Fig. 9. Real part of static pressure (normalized) pulsations in the inlet for circumferential mode with $f=f_1$, $m=15$ at N=75.5% operational conditions: a - integration surface; b - center of microphones arc

Calculation was performed for all modes, shown in fig. 8. In the fig. 9 the real part of complex static pressure

(normalized) for mode (86,15) in the inlet for N=75.5% operational condition is shown.

To compute tone noise radiation in the far field Ffowcs Williams and Hawkins method was used. Black curve in the fig. 9 shows the position of the integration surface. Pressure pulsations were calculated in the points placed along the arc with radius equal to 4 m with the center in the point of intersection between the surface, containing tips of the leading edges of fan rotor blades, and the axis of shaft rotation. The centre of the arc was shown in fig. 9. The points had uniform angular distribution within 1-90 degrees with 1 degrees spacing.

The comparison with experimental data

The results of calculation were compared with the results of the experiment for the fan model in the CIAM test rig C-3A. Comparison was performed for 12 microphones placed at the same distance from the fan, as in the computation. As an initial data for comparison we used narrowband spectra for these microphones obtained in the experiment. The frequency bands of the spectra were equal to 19.5 Hz. On the basis of these spectra were calculated directivity diagrams for the tone noise of harmonics under consideration.

The comparison between the results of the calculations for different operational conditions is presented in fig. 10a-d. In the figure the directivity diagrams for both the computation and the experiment for frequencies f_2-f_1 , f_2 , f_2+f_1 and f_2+2f_1 at operational conditions N=53.9% and N=75.5% are shown. In general we see good correspondence between the calculation and the experiment. However the significant deviation of the result of computation from experiment for N=75.5% operational conditions for angles corresponding to 80 and 90 degrees should be noted. This deviation can be explained by insufficient resolution of the grid in the radial direction.

According to the experimental results the maximum sound pressure levels at operational conditions N=53.9% are observed at the frequencies f_2+f_1 and f_2+2f_1 . For the N=75.5% the maximum sound pressure levels are observed at f_2 and f_2+f_1 . The results of the calculation shows maximum sound pressure levels for N=53.9% at f_2+f_1 and for N=75.5% at f_2 .

Fig. 10. Comparison between computational and experimental directivity diagrams in a forward hemisphere

Analysis of the computational results

The first problem which the authors would like to address is the influence of the number of harmonic fragments on the computational results at $N=53.9\%$ operational conditions. Comparison between the results of calculations for 46 and 67 harmonic fragments shows that the most significant deviations between them is observed for harmonics with frequencies f_2-f_1 and f_2 . The directivity diagrams for this harmonics corresponding to different calculations and to the experimental data are presented in fig. 11. In general the sound pressure levels grow with the increase of number of harmonic fragments. It seems that the results for 67 harmonic fragments are closer to the experimental data, though at most angles the differences between directivity diagrams are quite small.

The results can be explained on the bases of the results of the modal decompositions on the surface in front of the booster IGV. The comparison between the decompositions

showed that the only significant change in them with the increase of the number of harmonic fragments is the appearance of mode (68,-3), radiated from the booster stage. Though the power of the mode is much less, than the power of (86,15) mode, its contribution is enough to explain the difference in the directivity diagrams.

The calculations for various other sets of harmonic fragments were also performed. The analysis of their results showed, that the further increase of the number of harmonic fragments led to insignificant changes in the computation results.

The numerical investigation of the first booster stage tone noise at $N=75.5\%$ operational conditions also has been performed for different sets of harmonic fragments. However those calculations have not led to significantly different results.

Fig. 11. The directivity diagrams for the tone with frequency a) $f = -f_1+f_2$ and b) f_2 for calculations with 67 and 46 harmonic fragments (operational conditions $N=53.9\%$).

The comparison between the data for $N=53.9\%$ and $N=75.5\%$ operational conditions shows, that in general both experimental and computational curves for the sound pressure levels for the second operational conditions lays below the correspondent curves for the first one. It from the first glance radically contradicts with the general idea that the noise of the stage grows with the increase of the rotation speed. Also the significant difference in the distribution of energy between tones is observed.

To explain these effects it is possible to use the results of modal analysis on the surfaces in front the fan in front of the booster IGV and downstream the stage.

First let us consider the sound power on the surface in front of the booster IGV. It is more convenient to analyze the sound power of the stage on this surface, as in it the

power is distributed on lower number of modes in the bounded frequency range. The analysis showed that on the surface the sound power at operational condition N=75.5% is 0.5 dB higher than those for N=53.9% operational conditions. The increase of power is unexpectedly small. However we can compare these results with the results of the modal analyses downstream the fan. At the surface the calculated power of most intensive acoustic modes is 6.7 dB higher for N=75.5% operational conditions. The overall growth of sound power is 6 dB. Thus it is possible to conclude, that so insignificant increase of power in the entrance of core duct is caused by the significant reduction of relative part of sound power radiated upstream, with the increase of shaft rotation speed. The similar situation with the dependence of the relative part of sound power radiated upstream from the shift rotation speed was observed for subsonic counter-rotating fan [19].

For some modes the power radiated upstream even decreases. For example, for (86,15) the sound power radiated upstream, obtained in the modal analysis on the surface in front of booster IGV, decreased on 4.2 dB at N=75.5% operational conditions. However the sound power of mode radiated both upstream and downstream increased on 7 dB. The definite growth of amplitudes of pulsations, corresponding to the mode in the booster stage is clearly seen in fig. 7.

Fig. 12. Comparison of the results of the modal analysis on the surfaces in front of the fan (Surf. 1) and in front of the booster IGV (Surf. 2)

However, as it was shown earlier, the sound power levels of the most intensive tones, calculated on the surface in front of the fan, decreased on 2.6 dB. The analyses showed, that the effect is caused by stronger scattering of modes with negative circumferential orders with the fan rotor at N=75.5% operational conditions. Let's illustrate it on the example of the family of modes arising in the interaction between the fan rotor, rotor of the booster stage and its stator. For this modes $j^2=86+a*18$ and $m=-14+a*18$. In fig. 12 is presented the distribution of sound powers between these modes on the surfaces placed in front of the fan and in front of the booster IGV. The modes which power levels are lower than those of the strongest modes on more than 25 dB are not shown. It is possible to conclude, that in general for the N=75.5% operational conditions the sound power for this family of modes increased on 2.3 dB in comparison with N=53.9%

operational condition, but it became distributed on much higher frequency range. The slight reduce of power on the surface in front the fan is caused by the reflections from the fan rotor. Probably the intensity of the scattering is determined by the orientations of wave fronts of scattered disturbances relative to the fan rotor blades [20].

Finally we can conclude, that for the fan model under consideration the decrease of sound power levels of most intensive tones, connected with the noise of booster stages, with the increase of shaft rotation speed is caused first of all by the significant reduction of the relative part of sound power radiated upstream by the booster stage. Nevertheless the overall sound power of booster stage grows as the rotation frequency grows. Also the important role plays the scattering of modes, generated by the booster stage by the fan rotor with the significant increase of their frequency.

CONCLUSION

The results of the numerical investigation of the first booster stage tone noise for two operational conditions N=53% and N=75.5% are presented. The investigation was performed using the linear frequency domain method, developed in CIAM. The results of the calculation were compared with the experimental data. In general for both operational conditions the results of comparison can be treated as satisfactory. It was shown that sound power levels of most intensive tones, connected with the noise of the first booster stage are lower at N=75.5% than at N=53.9% operational conditions. Analysis of the computational data showed that the decrease of the sound power is caused by two different processes. First of all the increase of shaft rotation speed is accomplished by the significant reduction of the relative part of sound power radiated upstream by the booster stage. For some modes the significant increase of overall radiated power is connected with the decrease of absolute value of power, radiated upstream. The second process is the interaction of modes with the fan rotor, which is stronger for N=75.5% operational conditions. The modes with negative circumferential orders, radiated from core duct, can be scattered by the rotor at much higher frequency range than at N=53.9% operational conditions, thus reducing the power of individual modes in the inlet.

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